

LEXICO-SEMANTIC SIMILARITIES AND DIFFERENCES IN THE USE OF HYPONYMY IN THE ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT:

This article explores the lexico-semantic features of hyponymy in the English and Uzbek languages, highlighting their similarities and differences in organizing vocabulary and reflecting cultural, cognitive, and communicative contexts. Through the analysis of hierarchical structures, semantic taxonomy, and the role of hyponymy in language processing, the study reveals how both languages use hypernym-hyponym relationships to classify and convey meaning.

Keywords: Hyponymy, hierarchical structure, semantic taxonomy, natural language processing.

Introduction. Meaning, central to the study of language, is a concept that has occupied the minds of linguists and philosophers for centuries. Understanding how words and phrases convey meaning is a fundamental aspect of linguistics. Linguistic semantics is the study of how languages organize and express meanings [1]. Hyponymy, a fundamental semantic relationship in which the meaning of one word (the hyponym) is included within the meaning of a broader category (the hypernym), plays a critical role in organizing vocabulary in both English and Uzbek. When analyzing the vocabulary of a language as a systematic structure, it's crucial to consider the hypo-hyperonymic relationships of lexemes. This involves understanding the meanings of lexemes, which are terms for objects and events in nature and society, and using these meanings to both generalize and distinguish between concepts [2]. Exploring the lexico-semantic features of hyponymy in these languages reveals how each language reflects its cultural, cognitive, and communicative contexts.

We begin our analysis by exploring the lexico-semantic similarities and differences in how hyponymy is utilized in both languages.

Hierarchical Structure: Both English and Uzbek use a hierarchical structure to organize vocabulary. This system arranges words from the most general (hypernyms) to

the most specific (hyponyms), aiding in communication and knowledge organization. For example, “furniture” in English and “jihoz” in Uzbek are hypernyms for words like “bed” and “yotoq” respectively.

- Furniture —> bed, sofa, chair
- Jihoz —> yotoq, divan, kursi (stul)

Moreover, in both languages hyponymy involves entailment and it is content dependent. Entailment in hyponymy refers to the logical relationship where the truth of one proposition (a hyponym) guarantees the truth of another (its hypernym). For instance, “I saw a owl yesterday” entails “I saw a bird yesterday” but not vice versa because “owl” is a “bird” but a “bird” is not always an “owl”, it could be sparrow, parrots, etc and it depends on context. Similarly, in Uzbek, “Kecha boyqushni ko‘rdim” entails “Kecha qushni ko‘rdim”.

Semantic taxonomy: Semantic taxonomy is the classification of words and concepts in a language based on their meanings and relationships. English and Uzbek, while having different linguistic foundations and cultural settings, both use semantic taxonomies to arrange information. English semantic taxonomy often follows traditional linguistic roots derived from Latin, Greek, and Germanic origins, categorizing concepts broadly into nouns, verbs, adjectives, etc., and then into more specific groups based on semantic features. Uzbek taxonomy is deeply influenced by the cultural, historical, and geographical context of Central Asia. Terms related to agriculture, nomadic lifestyles, and local flora and fauna are particularly detailed. Semantic changes and the development of hyponyms in English are heavily influenced by technological and scientific advancements. New technologies and global interactions frequently introduce new terms into the lexicon. For example, the word “grandfamily” means a family in which one or more children live and are raised by their grandparents or “Blursday” is a day that is hard to distinguish from previous days, or the occurrence of days running together [3].

Usage in language processing: The lexical and semantic features of hyponyms and hypernyms play a critical role in language processing, both for human cognition and in computational linguistics applications such as natural language processing (NLP). Natural language processing (NLP) refers to a computer program's ability to interpret human language as it is spoken and written, also known as natural language. It is a component of artificial intelligence (AI) [4]. In both English and Uzbek, understanding

the relationship between hyponyms and hypernyms is important for tasks like named entity recognition where entities need to be classified into categories (hyponyms) under broader concepts (hypernyms).

Both languages involve sophisticated handling of polysemy and homonymy, in which words can have numerous meanings depending on context. For example, the English word “bank” might refer to a financial institution or the edge of a river, while in Uzbek, “ot” could mean either a name or an animal, requiring context for correct interpretation. In both English and Uzbek, polysemy demonstrates how a single word can have numerous related meanings (e.g. “mouse” (animal) and “mouse” (computer device) or “og‘iz” - “odamning og‘zi” (someone’s mouth) and “qopning og‘zi” (the mouth of the sack)). The link between hyponyms and polysemy remains consistent, as distinct meanings might have their own sets of hyponyms. Homonymy in both languages complicates the hyponym-hypernym relationship by introducing words that, while identical in form, belong to completely different semantic areas (e.g. “bat” (an animal) and “bat” (sport instrument) or “olma” (an apple) and “olma” (do not take)). To tell them apart, you must first comprehend the context.

Besides, the agglutinative character of the Uzbek language enables it to produce detailed lexical items by adding affixes, which is critical for language processing in tasks such as stemming and lemmatization, where word forms must be broken down and understood based on their components. For instance: “Daraxtzor” (grove), from “daraxt” (tree) or “kitobxon” (book reader) from “kitob” (book) shows how new words form by affixation. Another example, the word “mustahkamlashtiramiz” breaks down into morphemes as “mustahkam+lashtira+miz”. It starts with the adjective “mustahkam” (strong), turns into a verb with “mustahkamlashtirmoq” (to make strong), and then adds the causative suffix “+lashtira” (to cause to make). The ending “+miz” signifies “we”, “us”, indicating a collective action. The complete translation of “mustahkamlashtiramiz” in English would be “we will make it strong” [5].

Better understanding and implementation of hyponymic relationships can improve the contextual accuracy of machine translations between English and Uzbek. Both languages need culturally and contextually aware NLP systems. For English, handling idiomatic expressions is crucial, whereas for Uzbek, incorporating terms with deep cultural significance is essential. Many Uzbek hyponyms reflect distinct cultural or regional realities, which must be taken into account during language processing to

ensure cultural relevance and accuracy. Translating technical or scientific terms often requires creating new terms in Uzbek or using existing ones that capture the precise meaning. For example, “deciduous trees” might be directly translated or described functionally to convey the concept clearly in Uzbek. Certain local agricultural terms or native species might not have direct English equivalents and may need descriptive translations or footnotes to convey the full meaning.

Cultural context and vocabulary: As a global lingua franca with a rich history of borrowing from other languages, English has a very extensive vocabulary, including a broad array of hyponyms within any given hypernym category. This diversity can reflect the multicultural nature of English-speaking societies. For example, English has multiple words for ski vocabulary and snow equipment.

- “Liftie” - a person who runs a ski lift;
- “Snowplow” - a tool or vehicle that pushes thick snow off highways;
- “Chute” - a steep, narrow slope with high sides and off-piste;
- “Moguls” - snow bumps that are groomed into a ski run for a freestyle challenge [6].

The Uzbek language contains more culturally peculiar hyponyms that represent Central Asia's distinct geographic, historical, and social environment. Hyponymic relationships may emphasize things or categories that are particularly significant in Uzbek culture. For example, Uzbek language has several particular names for different sorts of fabrics or irrigation methods utilized in agriculture that are culturally important. For example, there are several specific hyponyms naming fabrics in Uzbek:

- “Bo‘z” - plain fabric made from loose-spun cotton thread;
- “Olacha” - thin striped fabric; it is usually hand woven from cotton thread, sometimes from thread and silk;
- “Duxoba” - soft, smooth, fluffy fabric;
- “Beqasam” - striped fabric; it is usually woven from silk and arca yarn [7].

The specific categories emphasized in each language can reflect the environment and culture of the speakers. Uzbek may have more detailed categories for things that are common in Central Asia, while English might have broader categories influenced by a wider global exposure. In general, hyponymic patterns in both languages reflect cultural priorities - English has a global, broad range of influences, whereas Uzbek has a strong relationship to local geography and culture.

The analysis of hyponymy in English and Uzbek demonstrates the critical role of hierarchical structures and semantic relationships in organizing language and reflecting cultural identity. Both languages use hypernym-hyponym systems to categorize vocabulary, though cultural and historical contexts shape their specificity and development. The study underscores the importance of understanding these relationships for language processing, highlighting challenges such as polysemy, homonymy, and morphological complexity in English and Uzbek.

REFERENCES:

1. Kreidler C. W. *Introducing English Semantics*. Routledge, 1998.
2. Ne'matov H, Rasulov R. O'zbek tili sistem leksikologiyasi asoslari. Toshkent: O'qituvchi, 1995. B. 111-123.
3. D. New Words Drop! Get The First Look At Our Fall 2023 Collection Of Dictionary Additions. 2023, September 6. Dictionary.com. <https://www.dictionary.com/e/new-dictionary-words-fall-2023/>
4. Gillis A. S., Lutkevich B., Burns E. natural language processing (NLP). Enterprise AI. 2024, February 15. <https://www.techtarget.com/searchenterpriseai/definition/natural-language-processing-NLP>
5. Ismailov A. Sh., Shamsiyeva G., Abdurakhmonova N. Statistical machine translation proposal for Uzbek to English. // "Science and Education" Scientific Journal. 2021. ISSN 2181-0842. P. 213.
6. Skiing Vocabulary | Learn English. (n.d.). <https://www.englishclub.com/vocabulary/sports-skiing.php>
7. Ўзбекистон Миллий Энциклопедияси – QOMUS.INFO. <https://qomus.info/>.